

Figure S1 The pipeline of HGT identification in transcriptome. Eighty genomes of eucicots and four *Alnus* transcriptomes are packed as the first database to infer putative HGT sequences and orthogroups. Every orthogroup was aligned and trimmed to make maximum likelihood (ML) trees. Three databases for Ericales, Fagales, and Rosales are built to infer orthogroups and construct ML trees again. Finally the HGT sequences and phylogenetic placements are confirmed.

Figure S2 Representative HGT events in transcriptomes of *Boschniakia himalaica* and *B. rossica*. (a, b) Sequences of *B. himalaica* and *B. rossica* are nested in those of *Rhododendron* and *Alnus*, respectively. (c) The clade of *B. himalaica* and *B. rossica* is phylogenetically placed in Rosaceae. Horizontally transferred sequences are marked with parentheses. The expanded full phylogenetic trees are shown in Additional file 3 with Nos. OG0007337 (Ericales), OG0003343 (Fagales), and OG0000181 (Rosales).

FigureS3 (Continued)

Figure S4 Schematic organelle genome diagram of *B. himalaica* and *B. rossica*. The genes outside the circle are transcribed in the counterclockwise direction, and the genes inside the circle are transcribed in the clockwise direction. Different colors in genes represent different functions. The dark gray area and light gray area of the inner circle represent the ratio of GC content to AT content in the genome, respectively.

Figure S4 (Continued)

(a)

(b)

Figure S5 Multiple alignment of conserved genomic sequence with rearrangements of organelle genomes in five Orobanchaceae species. (a) mitogenomes. (b) plastomes.

Figure S6 Distribution of four types of repetitive sequences in *B. himalaica* (a) and *B. rossica* (b).

(a)

(b)

Figure S7 Foreign sequences of the mitogenomes of *Boschniokia himalaica* and *B. rossica*. (a) ML trees of plastid-derived and mitochondrial horizontally transferred gene fragments. Their extended trees can be found in Additional file 3. (b) The close taxa of foreign sequences in mitogenomes.

Figure S8 Sequence origin of the mitogenomes of five parasitic Orobanchaceae species. Bhim, *B. himalaica*; Bros, *B. rossica*; Aegi, *Aeginetia indica*; Cast, *Castilleja paramensis*; Perx, *Pedicularis rex*.